

Grids and Profiles in the CMIP Data Request -- First Meeting

Location: online, zoom

Time: see doodle: <https://doodle.com/poll/9ze2g24r9hzxdywf> , Monday 21st sept 2020, 16:00.

Present : Martin Juckes, Alison Pamment, Klaus Zimmermann, Charlotte Pascoe., Paul Durack

Background

The CMIP Data Request provides specifications for CMIP model output, but this is often in the form of code words or directives which need to be interpreted to create a valid CMIP data file. The additional information needed to make up valid CMIP files is split across a number of WIP white papers, the CF Conventions, CMOR documentation and CMOR code.

In some cases there are multiple options. For example, if data is requested on model levels, then there are many different approaches to vertical discretisation within the multi-model ensemble, and there is a specific CF-compliant formulation of the file metadata associated with each of these.

e.g. Example 4.3 of the CF Conventions:

```
float lev(lev) ;
  lev:long_name = "sigma at layer midpoints" ;
  lev:positive = "down" ;
  lev:standard_name = "atmosphere_sigma_coordinate" ;
  lev:formula_terms = "sigma: lev ps: PS ptop: PTOP" ;
  lev:computed_standard_name = "air_pressure" ;
```

A listing of the options supported by CMOR is here:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Njhnp-rAhQNb9lo4d_0YFUOdPttcPpjQec4R_7BMUH8/edit#gid=1854910047;

Repo for collecting stuff: <https://github.com/cmip6dr/GridsAndProfiles>

Meeting notes

KZ suggested creating a registry of model grids, so that each grid could have a unique identifier. Grid definitions in ES-DOC are freestyle and do not lend themselves to automated use. Some form of fingerprinting could be used to compare data grids against the registry.

Martin: cmip has CMOR implementations for cube-sphere and rotated pole.

AP asked about the role of UGRID. KZ suggested that UGRID could be a standard used within the registry.

MJ mentioned the need to cover for example, regular, cube sphere grids, etc.

Klaus: ORCA grids; can we include metrics for area calculation.

Klaus: is there an example of a CMIP6 grid with cube sphere?

Martin: will check?

KZ commented that for tripolar grids it is hard to identify precisely which grid is used. If detailed comparison is done, might be confused by rounding.

MJ asked if the problems would be resolved by a NetCDF file, e.g. of orography, which CMORised data plus some additional metadata?

KZ suggested that a file of weights for interpolation to the useful. MJ commented that it is difficult to reach agreement on how to deal with interpolation close to the coast. KZ commented that this applies to all masked variables. But the main thing is to store weights.¹

KZ discussed classification of grids used, and proposed a python script to put existing grids into classes.

Klaus: should we look at grid overlaps (as raised by Paul)? WOn't do this in first scan.

Follow up for Oct. 8th.

Actions:

KZ: progress report before Oct 8th. DONE: see minutes of 8th:

<https://zenodo.org/record/6347569>

MJ: check for cube-sphere grid in CMIP6 models. DONE: none found

CP: upload metafor grid mindmap to the github. DONE:

<https://github.com/cmip6dr/GridsAndProfiles/issues/1>

¹ There is some discussion on how to handle weights here:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1BfVVskAK9MAsoYstwFSWI2ZBt5mrO_NmCu7rLGDuL08/edit